

THE MECHANICAL TESTING OF CONTINUOUS FIBRE REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC PIPES

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SUMMARY: The results of tests on reinforced thermoplastic pipes, internally pressurised with closed end conditions, are reported. Because the fibres used for reinforcement are not infiltrated, a feature of the deformation at low pressures is a high degree of non-linearity. The behaviour can be understood if it is assumed that non-linear visco-elastic and plastic deformation of the polyethylene occurs without fibre loading over a range of strain required to straighten the fibre yarn. At higher strains load is increasingly borne by the fibres up to the point of rupture. The strain pressure relations are interpreted in terms of netting analysis and laminate theory.

KEYWORDS: reinforced thermoplastics, pressurised pipes, reinforcing tape, non-infiltrated fibres, non-linear deformation.

INTRODUCTION

Reinforced thermoplastic pipes (RTPs) possess an attractive combination of properties. They have good strength under internal pressure, flexibility in installation and good corrosion resistance. These features make RTPs attractive for replacing steel and glass fibre-reinforced thermosets. Possible applications include offshore flexible risers and umbilicals and onshore flow lines. The materials costs of RTPs greatly outweigh those of steel and glass reinforced epoxy but owing to the particular combination of properties of RTPs, resulting in ease of handling during installation, the total capital expenditure costs are comparable with other pipeline options. In addition, because of its good corrosion resistance, the life of an RTP may be up to four times longer than the equivalent steel pipeline in many operations. Consequently, there is much current interest in the development of RTP systems. The introduction of RTPs can be viewed as a development leading on from the polyethylene pipes that have replaced cast iron in low pressure gas and water distribution systems. The advantage of RTPs is that they have much higher pressure capacity, whilst retaining much of the bending flexibility of polyethylene.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

The RTPs were manufactured using a special composite tape (Fig. 1). This consists of non-infiltrated aramid yarn encapsulated in medium density polyethylene (MDPE) to form tape, 105 mm wide and 0.85 mm thick. The tape contains 0.32 volume fraction of fibres and has a

Young's modulus of 27.8 GPa in the fibre direction and 0.5 GPa in the transverse direction. The in-plane shear modulus is 0.4 GPa and the Poisson's ratio is 0.315 for transverse contraction in reaction to a strain applied parallel to the fibres. The tubes were manufactured using a pull-winding process in which the tape was wrapped around either a MDPE or a high density polyethylene (HDPE) liner to provide a reinforcement inclined at $\pm 55^\circ$ to the tube axis. An outer skin of MDPE was then added by an extrusion process. Tubes supplied by two manufacturers were tested. Specimens supplied by Wavin (MDPE liner) contained two tape layers (internal diameter 100 mm, total wall thickness of 25 mm). The tubes supplied by Tubes d'Aquitaine contained four tape layers over a HDPE liner with a MDPE skin (internal diameter 141 mm, total wall thickness 31.2 mm).

A particular problem in testing RTPs is attachment of the end fittings. Because of the difficulty in forming a strong adhesive bond with thermoplastics, mechanical methods of fitting are preferred. The Wavin RTPs were press fitted into PECAT fittings (supplied by WASK-RFM). These are steel-flanged end fittings with a steel core fitted with O-rings. The end closure for the Tubes d'Aquitaine RTP was made by cutting an external thread in the outer MDPE layer. A threaded aluminium fitting was screwed on over the tube end. The tubes were tested in 1.5 m lengths by hydraulically pressurising at a mean rate of 10 bar per minute in the region of linear behaviour.

Hoop strain was deduced from the mean change in the tube diameter measured at the centre of the specimen and at two other points 100 mm on either side. The changes in diameter were measured with linear displacement transducers held in special fittings. With the Wavin specimens, the axial strain was deduced from change in length of the tube measured with three linear displacement transducers spaced 120° apart around the circumference and connected to the end fittings. This measurement is liable to error if there is any slippage in the end fittings. The axial strain for the Tubes d'Aquitaine specimens were measured over a shorter gauge length using transducers attached to the tube surface with special fittings.

RESULTS

Examples of the strain-pressure relations are shown in Figs. 2. It is possible that the hoop strain increases linearly with pressure at very low pressures but on the pressure scale adopted for the tests the hoop strain is decidedly non-linear up to a strain of between 1.5 and 2%. Thus, a substantial hoop strain accumulates with relatively little pressure increase. At hoop strains larger than a critical value the pressure rises more rapidly for a given strain increment to give an approximately linear strain-pressure relation up to the burst point. These results can be rationalised if it is assumed that the aramid fibres do not begin to support the hoop stress until after the critical strain has accumulated. This is possible if the fibres within the yarn are initially slack and have to straighten to begin to support the load. The critical strain is required to take up the slack in the fibres and is here termed the "take up" strain. On this interpretation, the deformation observed in the non-linear region simply reflects the deformation of the polyethylene, without any effect of the fibres. An analytical model has been developed to

Fig. 1: Structure of reinforced thermoplastic pipes (RTPs)

Fig. 2: Strain-pressure curves. (a) Wavin specimen (b) Tubes d' Aquitain specimen

Fig. 3: Experimental data (points) fitted with composite curves (a) Wavin specimen (b) Tubes d'Aquitaine specimen

account for the size of the take up strain in terms of fibre characteristics [1] but this is not presented here.

In contrast to the hoop strain, the axial strain does not exhibit pronounced non-linearity in the pressure range from zero to 40 bar. In other words, as the tube inflates, with an increasing hoop deformation of the polyethylene, the axial strain increases by a much smaller amount. It will be argued below that the difference is due to the influence of the deviatoric stress components on plastic or non-linear visco-elastic deformation.

The axial strain-pressure relation in the Wavin specimen showed a degree of non-linearity at pressures greater than about 60 bar with a reduced slope at the higher pressures (Fig. 2 (a)). The axial strain in the Tubes d'Aquitaine specimen showed a small increase with pressure up to about 25 bar but reduced towards zero at higher pressures (Fig. 2 (b)).

The burst pressure was 128 bar for the Wavin specimen and 273 bar for the Tubes d'Aquitaine specimens. The form of the rupture was similar in all cases. It is probable that rupture begins when a critical fraction of the fibres in any location have fractured. Rupture then proceeds by necking of the polyethylene wall in the through-thickness direction. This is followed by extension of the rupture along one of the fibre directions accompanied by extrusion of fibres through the gap in the wall and depressurisation. The Wavin tubes exhibited a 150 mm long rupture after depressurisation. The length of rupture was slightly larger (200 mm) in the Tubes d'Aquitaine specimens and was found to zig-zag following both fibre directions alternately in the course of its development. The location of the rupture sites was found to vary. In some specimens the sites were located near the end fittings. In other specimens the rupture occurred closer to the central portion of the tube.

Analysis Of Deformation

For simplicity we assume the thin wall approximation for the stresses so that the effect of radial pressure is ignored. We also consider membrane stresses only and ignore bending stresses that might arise, for example, from the constraints exerted by the end fittings [2]. The reference coordinates are θ for the circumferential direction, r for the radial direction and z for the axial direction. The system is statically determinate, so with the thin wall approximation for a closed end cylinder, diameter D and wall thickness t the applied stress components are: $\sigma_{\theta\theta} = \sigma_h$, $\sigma_{rr} = 0$, and $\sigma_{zz} = \frac{1}{2}\sigma_h$, where $\sigma_h = pD/2t$.

Plastic or Non-linear Visco-elastic Deformation

In the pressure and strain range before the take up strain has accumulated the deformation is believed to reflect only the deformation of the polyethylene, with no influence exerted by the fibres. This idea is supported by the curve shown in Fig 3(a) of stress-strain data for MDPE tubes [3] fitted to the non-linear deformation observed in the RTP. However, no large scale, non-linear deformation is indicated by the axial strain at low pressures. The difference between the hoop and axial strain behaviour is believed to arise from the response of the material to the deviatoric stress components, as discussed below.

Pressure cycling tests and creep tests [1] have revealed that the non-linear deformation is composed of both plastic and non-linear visco-elastic components. Approximately, one half of the hoop strain observed in the take up region is plastic and irreversible. The other half of the

non-linear strain is reversible and rate and time dependent. The axial strain in the take up region was also found to be visco-elastic, but on a much smaller scale than the hoop strain.

It is well known that plastic deformation responds only to the deviatoric components of stress (e.g. ref. 4). We assume here that the same is true for non-linear, visco-elastic deformation. Since the hydrostatic stress component is equal to $\frac{1}{2}\sigma_h$, the deviatoric components are: $s_{\theta\theta} = \frac{1}{2}\sigma_h$, $s_{rr} = -\frac{1}{2}\sigma_h$ and $s_{zz} = 0$. The Prandtl-Reuss equations [4] give the total elastic-plastic strain rates in terms of the stress rates and the deviatoric stress components, i.e.

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{e}_{\theta\theta} &= \frac{1}{E}[\dot{\sigma}_{\theta\theta} - \nu(\dot{\sigma}_{rr} + \dot{\sigma}_{zz})] + \lambda s_{\theta\theta} , \\ \dot{e}_{rr} &= \frac{1}{E}[\dot{\sigma}_{rr} - \nu(\dot{\sigma}_{\theta\theta} + \dot{\sigma}_{zz})] + \lambda s_{rr} , \\ \dot{e}_{zz} &= \frac{1}{E}[\dot{\sigma}_{zz} - \nu(\dot{\sigma}_{\theta\theta} + \dot{\sigma}_{rr})] + \lambda s_{zz} ,\end{aligned}\quad (1)$$

where E is Young's modulus and ν is Poisson's ratio. The parameter λ can be considered to control the rate of plastic strain and has to be determined from a flow criterion for a full description of plasticity. However, in the present case we need only note that, by inspection of eqns. (1), plastic deformation cannot contribute a component to the axial strain e_{zz} because $s_{zz} = 0$. Thus plastic or visco-elastic deformation causes the tube to inflate with no change in axial length from these modes of deformation. The increase in the hoop strain from plasticity is entirely accommodated by a plastic contraction in the through-thickness direction.

Elastic Deformation at Strains Above the Take Up Strain

When the take up strain has been exceeded, the overall deformation becomes elastic again. The aramid fibres now support an increasing proportion of the hoop force and constrain further deformation of the yielded polyethylene. Since the polyethylene is in the plastic state it can support only a portion of the total load to an extent determined by its yield or flow stress. The elastic deformation can thus be approximated by ignoring the polyethylene and considering only the fibres. In this case it is appropriate to use netting analysis [5,6]. Treating the reinforcing tape as an entity, the netting analysis prediction for both the hoop and axial strain is

$$e_{\theta\theta} = e_{zz} = \frac{3}{2} \frac{\sigma_h}{E_t V_t} , \quad (2)$$

where E_t is the longitudinal Young's modulus of the reinforcing tape and V_t is the volume fraction of the tape. This gives a reasonable fit for the slope of the hoop strain-pressure curve for the Wavin specimen if an offset strain of 1.6% is added to allow for the take up strain (Fig. 3(a)). Netting analysis also predicts that the axial strain is equal to the hoop strain. This is not the case at lower pressures, but at pressures greater than about 70 bar, netting analysis gives a reasonable approximation to the *slope* of the axial strain-pressure relation (Fig. 3(a)).

The results for the Tubes d'Aquitaine specimen are more difficult to explain. The constitution of the Wavin and Tubes d'Aquitaine specimens are similar, and although there may be small

differences owing to the different manufacturing routes, it is difficult to explain why there should be such a large difference in the hoop to axial strain ratios.

An alternative method of predicting the pressure-strain relation is to use laminate analysis. This is based on the assumption of linear elasticity, which is obviously not the case here. However, laminate analysis can be applied in a loose way, if representative rather than actual elastic constants are adopted for the matrix-related elastic constants.

The orthotropic elastic constants for a laminae are denoted by the q symbols where $q_{11} = E_L/(1-\nu_{LT}\nu_{TL})$, $q_{22} = E_T/(1-\nu_{LT}\nu_{TL})$, $q_{12} = \nu_{LT}E_L/(1-\nu_{LT}\nu_{TL})$ and $q_{66} = G_{LT}$. Here, E_L is Young's modulus in a direction parallel to the fibres, E_T is Young's modulus transverse to the fibres and G_{LT} is the in-plane shear modulus, where ν_{LT} and ν_{TL} are the in-plane Poisson's ratios.

The elastic constants for the laminate referred to the hoop and axial reference axes are given by the rotation formulae [6,7]

$$\begin{aligned} Q_{11} &= q_{11}\cos^4\phi + 2(q_{12} + 2q_{66})\sin^2\phi\cos^2\phi + q_{22}\sin^4\phi, \\ Q_{22} &= q_{11}\sin^4\phi + 2(q_{12} + 2q_{66})\sin^2\phi\cos^2\phi + q_{22}\cos^4\phi, \\ Q_{12} &= q_{12}(\sin^4\phi + \cos^4\phi) + (q_{11} + q_{22} - 4q_{66})\sin^2\phi\cos^2\phi, \\ Q_{66} &= (q_{11} + q_{22} - 2q_{12} - 2q_{66})\sin^2\phi\cos^2\phi + q_{66}(\sin^4\phi + \cos^4\phi), \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where ϕ is the magnitude of the angle between the z -axis and the fibre directions. The constants in (3) allow the stress to be calculated in terms of a given strain. To obtain the strain in terms of a given applied stress requires the matrix associated with the Q values in (3) to be inverted. For the present case of a biaxial stress with $\sigma_h = \sigma_{\theta\theta} = 2\sigma_{zz}$ we have

$$e_{zz} = \sigma_h \frac{\frac{1}{2}Q_{22} - Q_{12}}{Q_{11}Q_{22} - Q_{12}^2}, \quad (4)$$

$$e_{\theta\theta} = \sigma_h \frac{Q_{11} - \frac{1}{2}Q_{12}}{Q_{11}Q_{22} - Q_{12}^2}.$$

Numerical evaluation using eqns. (3) and (4) for various test cases shows that the strain ratios are inordinately sensitive to the values of the matrix-related constants when ϕ is close to the special angle $\phi = \arctan(\sqrt{2}) = 54.74^\circ$ (the ideal netting angle). However, numerical examples do not highlight the interaction of different factors in producing this sensitivity. This interaction is more clearly seen using analytical expressions that result from a consideration of some limiting cases.

Imagine that those elastic constants that are controlled mainly by the properties of the matrix material (q_{12} , q_{22} and q_{66}) become very small, to the extent that second order terms (e.g. q_{22}^2 , $q_{12}q_{22}$, $q_{12}q_{66}$ or any similar products where the subscripts 2 or 6 appear twice or in combination) can be ignored. With this approximation, and with ϕ taken to be equal to $\arctan(\sqrt{2})$, eqns. (3)

and (4) can be used to obtain simpler analytical expressions. After some algebraic manipulation, the details of which are not shown here, we obtain:

$$e_{zz} = \frac{3}{2} \frac{\sigma_h}{E_L} \frac{[8 - (1 + 2\nu_{LT})E_T / G_{LT}]}{[8 + E_T / G_{LT}]}, \quad (5)$$

$$e_{\theta\theta} = \frac{3}{2} \frac{\sigma_h}{E_L} \frac{[8 + (2 + \nu_{LT})E_T / G_{LT}]}{[8 + E_T / G_{LT}]}.$$

The effect of taking various limits can now be obtained by inspection of eqn. (5). The key parameter is the ratio E_T/G_{LT} .

(i) If E_T goes to zero whilst G_{LT} remains finite, both e_{zz} and e_{θ} go to the limiting value $3/2 \sigma_h/E_L$, i.e. the strain ratio is unity. If the term E_L is identified with $E_t V_t$ the result is identical to that of netting analysis.

(ii) If G_{LT} goes to zero whilst E_T remains finite, the limiting strain values are

$$e_{zz} = -\frac{3}{2}(1 + 2\nu_{LT})\sigma_h / E_L, \quad (6)$$

$$e_{\theta\theta} = \frac{3}{2}(2 + \nu_{LT})\sigma_h / E_L.$$

In this case, the hoop strain is more than twice the value predicted by netting analysis and the axial strain is negative.

(iii) Another special case worth investigating is when the axial strain is zero. The ratio of E_T to G_{LT} where this occurs can be obtained from eqn. (5). The following particular result for the hoop strain then obtains when $e_{zz} = 0$:

$$e_{\theta\theta} = \frac{9}{4} \frac{\sigma_h}{E_L}. \quad (7)$$

In this case, in addition to the fact that the axial strain has been set to zero, the predicted hoop strain is about 50% larger than the netting analysis result.

Equation (7) was fitted to the results for the Tubes d'Aquitaine specimen (Fig. 3(b)). Although the axial strain corresponds approximately with the experimental data, as is imposed by adopting eqn. (7), the predicted hoop strain is larger than is observed experimentally. On the other hand, although the netting analysis prediction (with 1.4% offset) fits the observed hoop strain well, the predicted axial strain does not correspond with the experimental observations.

DISCUSSION

The take up strain observed in the present work is a consequence of the reinforcing fibres not being infiltrated. In contrast with the present results, thermoplastic tubes reinforced with glass

fibres that *are* infiltrated do not exhibit the non-linear behaviour shown in Fig. 2 [8]. In the present case, the polyethylene components have to yield in order load the fibres. Although yielding of the polyethylene produces a larger hoop strain than would otherwise occur with fully infiltrated fibres, the associated properties confer useful, additional advantages on RTPs. For example, the flexural resistance of the tubes is low as a consequence of the non-infiltration. Thus, the tubes are easily coiled, giving considerable flexibility in installation. In addition, if an RTP is collapsed by external pressure or concentrated loads, its subsequent ability to contain high pressure is very little affected [1].

At strains greater than the take up strain, the hoop strain behaves as predicted by netting analysis. However, the axial strain as a function of pressure is observed to be less predictable. This is not entirely unexpected, since in netting analysis the fibres can only support the load when they are inclined at exactly the ideal angle, i.e. some shear resistance is required to compensate for any slight deviation from the ideal angle. Laminate analysis is preferred in this case although there is uncertainty about its application to fibres in a non-linear matrix. When the matrix-related elastic constants become very small, as might be considered an approximation when the matrix is plastic, the predicted strain ratio is rather sensitive to the ratio of the notional transverse and shear moduli. Thus, a full analysis of elastic fibres in a non-linear, yielding matrix is required to resolve this point.

CONCLUSIONS

Pressure tests have been carried out on closed end reinforced thermoplastic pipes.

(ii) The hoop strain-pressure relation shows a high degree of non-linearity in the early stages of deformation. Because the fibres are not infiltrated, the polyethylene has to yield by plastic and non-linear visco-elastic deformation to load the fibres.

(iii) The axial strain does not exhibit non-linearity in the low pressure region because the deviatoric component of stress in the axial direction is zero.

(iv) Netting analysis can account for the hoop strain at strains greater than the take up strain.

(v) The axial strain is less predictable than the hoop strain. Some approximations derived from laminate analysis have been used to investigate this point.

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